

SOUNDCAPSULE: THE STUDY OF REMINISCENCE TRIGGERED BY UTILIZING SOUND MEDIA AND TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

With dramatically increasing amount of digital recordings, it becomes impossible to revisit all digital data that were ever significant in our life. However, a time capsule is often used as a historic cache or a method to communicate with future people. We argue that successfully forming digital material into a time capsule needs to understand both whether its content tends to be forgotten easily and whether its future evocation is significant. Our aim is to explore appropriate digital material to facilitate serendipitous reminiscence over time and space. We performed three pre-studies to support our design, SoundCapsule, a mobile phone application. Ten participants were invited to experience receiving random calls from their own recordings three months ago in their daily life. Qualitative research results indicate that most participants express positive surprise when receiving a SoundCapsule. This paper demonstrates how technology-mediated sound is formed to trigger everyday reminiscence.

Keywords: Reminiscence, Serendipity, SoundCapsule

INTRODUCTION

Down through the ages, people have the habit of collecting, and collecting itself is an accumulation and extension of the memory and also a behavior of recording of the life (Kalnikaitė, Sellen, Whittaker, & Kirk, 2010). Through a review of these objects and records, people evoke their memories. However, with the vigorous development of technology, people are getting used to using electronic devices to store their own memories of life into digital format, and when they need something, they will search it from those devices. Although today's progress in

technology is helpful for storing a large number of daily life data, these digital data become too enormous and burdensome. Moreover, because they are stored in electronic devices, people are likely to forget them. Namely, that it's difficult to have a connection with old memories makes people trapped in the myth of the cyber world. As what Petrelli and Whittaker (2010a) indicate, digital collection is invisible and inaccessible in respect of memories, and thus it is not like a common physical object that can become naturally a part of our daily life to evoke our old memories. That's why many people would prefer to choose a physical object when they are asked to choose an item to evoke their memories (Petrelli, Hoven, & Whittaker, 2009).

Figure 1. Left - SoundCapsule icon on Android platform, Right - homepage of SoundCapsule.

On the other hand, most studies about evoking of memories adopt physical objects (souvenir or daily object) and digital visual media (image, video and text) as major materials to evoke memories. According to the overview of most studies, we find that few studies used sound media as the theme. Probably because it's not really convenient to use and to carry a recording device, people seldom use

sound media as a material of recording. In our daily life, sound and image media co-exist and surround us. This inseparable relationship affects people's perception, but strangely people often preserve more visual and tactile information and neglect the sound. This also indicates that the sound is still only an accessory to the image in people's subconsciousness.

Therefore, in this paper we do not intend to develop a new physical object. We attempt to discuss how to use audio clips to recall the memory with new ways. We explore the concept of *time capsule* of sonic that we called 'SoundCapsule' (figure1), which allows people to keep recording and storing the fragments of their daily life. We combine the current personal belongings, mobile phone, and run it on Android platform. Then it would randomly play the recorded sound in the future to evoke our memories and make us re-experience the feelings about the past and so on. We expect to use the device to study how digital sound can engender and enhance reminiscing.

Besides, most technological devices of evoking of memories are designed to ask people to actively select the information they want and directly play it. This kind of foreground evocating activity is a purposeful behavior and its result is predictable so that there will be no surprise at all. On the contrary, the software of SoundCapsule will make the users give up their right of making choice and allow the software program itself to execute it instead. This will create an implicit interaction by random effects. That is, because users cannot predict the time, space and sound fragments, they will feel more surprised and excited when they receive the information. As Tuck Wah Leong (2008, 2009) asserts, "Using a random way can variably evoke the memories and stimulate the imagination, and connect with some unexpected things." Thus using a random way in time domain is highlighted in our design to evoke serendipitous reminiscence.

RELATED WORK

In the current academic papers, there are already a number of related works that have tackled how to build memory access and links through today's

technology and presented various designs. Here, we provide some points of view as the reference.

Lifelogging (Kalnikaitė et al., 2010) appeared few years ago. Users have to wear a camera and use GPS to automatically record their life information in the remote computer. When users want to search some old memories, they link to the website of Lifelogging, and then they can search the past events. However, it is worth noting that it focuses on the convenience of technology and neglects the intentions that people desire to keep their things in the form of memory, and thus it usually fails to touch people's hearts.

Besides, Hiroshi Ishii (1997) proposed a new interface mode, Tangible User Interface(TUI), and demonstrated how to connect a physical object with the digital information to present a new interaction mode. Based on this concept, there are a lot of studies that combine personal physical objects with digital information to carry out the design of memory access. For example, Memory Box (Stevens, Abowd, Truong, & Vollmer, 2003) hides the digital information in a physical object and the monitor outside will show the digital information about this physical object when it is taken out of the glass box. Another example, Cara Clock (Uriu, Shiratori, Hashimoto, Ishibashi, & Okude, 2009) saves and shares the photos collected by the family, and what is interesting is that when different pieces of Cara Clock are connected simultaneously, the photos of each generation at the same age will be shown to allow the family members to compare the difference between the generations. With Memodules (Mugellini, Rubegni, Gerardi, & Khaled, 2007), people can put the souvenirs on the platform with RFID reader, and then the tag-related events and photos will be shown and the users can share them simultaneously with others. Moreover, when people put their holiday photos on the device called audioprint player (Frohlich & Fennell, 2007) with RFID reader, the sound recorded during the holiday will be played, and this sound can be shared with family and friends without using any other electronic equipment.

However, there are also some studies that use sounds as major media to evoke memories. For

example, the sound souvenir FM radio (Petrelli, Villar, Kalnikaite, Dib, & Whittaker, 2010b) allows users to adjust the sound channels through the transformed old radio and play the sound of the past holidays to re-experience the old memories. Sonic Gems, designed by Oleksik and Brown (2008), hide the sound in capsule-shaped containers, which connect to a bowl-shaped container embedded with Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technology. Whenever a capsule is picked, the sound inside this capsule will be triggered and played.

Besides, there are some designs that use a random way to represent the memories to actively arouse our daily life memories. The Other Brother (Helmes, Hummels, & Sellen, 2009) is a device that rotates automatically toward the orientation of loudest sounds and spontaneously records people's voice and video in a social occasion with a third-person view. Then through environmental stimulation it will play the fragments of the old sound at random to enable re-experience. Pensieve (Peesapati, Schwanda, Schultz, Lepage, Jeong, & Cosley, 2010) is a system that supports everyday reminiscence by emailing memory triggers containing digital contents posted previously on social websites. Autobiographical memories extracted from social media are effectively constructed and experienced in a serendipitous way when ecology of digital devices is ubiquitous in our everyday lives.

Summing up what we found in the above studies, we set three key points for our design: (1) to combine physical objects with digital information; (2) to adopt a random way to make the process of memory evocation produce some surprises; (3) to use audio media as a material to recall the memories.

According to the references above, we find that currently most media that are used to evoke memories are visual media (text, image, video) and physical objects. Of course, there are few cases in which audio media are mainly used but these cases rarely explain the features about the connection between audio media and the evoking of memories. Moreover, different effects of memory evocation caused by digital technologies such as visual and audio media are seldom discussed. Thus, before

carrying out the design of SoundCapsule, we want to understand whether audio media are suitable materials for the evocation of memories, know more about the features of sound, and find whether audio media will present different characteristics from those produced by visual media.

Therefore, we had three pre-studies to explore respectively the following three respects of audio media: (1) to compare the different degrees of oblivion in respect of memories between audio media and visual media; (2) to compare the different degrees of recall in respect of memories between audio media and visual media; (3) to know more about how the degrees of recall relate to the type of audio media and the type of space. In the following paragraphs, we will explain in detail the study methods and procedures in each stage. Of special notice is that the former two studies focused on the sensory memory rather than long-term and short-term memories. Finally, after each study was done, we had interviews the participants in order to know better and more about how visual media and audio media recalled their different feelings about the past. Moreover, another key point in our future study is that we want to know how the participants felt about the evocation of the emotional memories when they re-heard the recorded sound.

EXPLORATORY RESEARCH

Pre-study One was to compare the different degrees of forgetting in respect of memories between audio media and visual media. We designed a memory task similar to "free recall" in psychology (Memory, 2011) and invited 10 participants to carry out the study (Figure2). Firstly, it's about auditory memory. The participants were given 10 minutes to listen to 10 different sounds. Then they were invited to take a break for 30 minutes. Then they were asked to recall the sounds they had just listened and write them down on paper. Secondly, the participants were given 10 minutes to watch 10 different pictures, and then 30 minutes for a rest. Later, they were asked to recall the pictures they had just watched and write them down on paper. Finally, we conducted profound interviews with these participants.

Figure2. Studying process of pre-study One

Pre-study Two was to compare the different degrees of recall in respect of memories between audio media and visual media (Figure3). We adopted a memory task modified from “paired associate learning” in psychology (Memory, 2011) and invited 15 participants to carry out the study. The study was divided into two tasks, that is, Task A (using sound to evoke image) and Task B (using image to evoke sound), and each task was given 10 minutes. When Task A was done, the participants had 30 minutes for a break. Then it’s time for Task B. In both tasks participants were asked to write their answers on paper. We then had interviews the participants.

Figure3. Studying process of pre-study Two

Pre-study Three was to investigate how the degrees of recall relate to the type of audio media and the type of space (Figure4). We invited 10 participants and provided each of them with a recording device in order to allow them to collect their own sounds. The participants were given 2 weeks to record sounds in 5 different types of places. They were told to record 4 different kinds of sounds and take photos in each place. According to Frohlich (2004), the sound is divided into ambience, dialogue, music and monologue. There were a total of 20 sound clips and 20 photos by each participant. One week later, all data were collected. One month later, we made interviews with the participants to discuss the recordings in order to explore how the degrees of evoking relate to the type of sound media and the type of space. Besides, when the participants re-listened to the sounds, they were asked to fill out a rating scale about the degrees of recall by examining their self-reported memories.

Figure4. Studying process of pre-study Three

LESSON LEARNED

The result of pre- study One shows that among the 10 participants, 7 persons had higher grades in respect of the image, 1 person had higher grades in

respect of the sound, and two persons had the same grades in both image and sound. The average time spent in watching the images was about 3 minutes, and the average time spent in listening to the sounds was about 8 minutes. We conclude that people need more time to remember the sounds but they tend to forget sounds more than images.

However, during the interviews with the participants after the study, we also find the reason why people forget sounds easily and we summarize it as follows: (1) if the sound cannot stimulate the users to create an image to connect it with the memories, the sound will be easily forgotten; (2) the sound is dynamic and it might create an ambiguity in the process of listening so that it is hard to be clearly identified; (3) some kinds of sounds are too common so that they are easily forgotten by people; (4) if there are no clues or prompts, people are not able to catch the key point of a sound.

According to the result of Pre-study Two, there are 7 persons who had evoked the visual memories by using sound; there are 6 persons who had evoked auditory memories by using images; there are 2 persons who had the same grades in both. This result shows that using sound is easier than using image for people to recall their memories of paired association. However, in the interviews, many participants were surprised that using sound could evoke visual memories to such a great extent. They indicated that the auditory perception might include more images than visual perception and sound could stimulate the users to have more images in their mind. Thus we know that the participants are used to using visual memories and paying less attention to auditory memories in general.

There is a total of 191 sounds collected in the Pre-study Three, including 50 ambient sounds, 44 pieces of music, 47 dialogues and 50 monologues. According to the result of the study, we find that the features in different spaces don’t really affect the degrees of the evoking of memories but different types of sounds affect memories more obviously.

According to the study, we find that the participants were surprised and felt positive emotions such as joy

and fun when they heard again the sounds they had recorded previously. Most participants thought that the dialogues and monologues were filled with more affective components and helpful for the evoking of past memories, and these were the types of sounds that they wanted to keep the most. As to the ambient sounds, they were filled with relatively less surprises and affective components, and thus they were regarded as clues and prompts. As for the pieces of music, they were useful for the evoking of memories only when a participant particularly liked them or had a special feeling about them.

DESIGN IMPLICATIONS AND FOUNDINGS

To sum up, the results of the three pre-studies above show that sound media are more forgettable and more evocable. Especially, the dialogues and monologues consist of more affective features. Moreover, we also find that when the participants were asked to evoke their memories by using sound media, they might create more images because they had to pay attention and listen to the recorded sounds so that their participation was increased. This is also the reason why in the process of evocation the participants were able to talk a lot about the context related to the memories and about the surprises created by the unexpected discoveries. Thus, the sound media are really suitable to be used as a material of the evoking of memories.

In addition, we also find that the relationship between the participants and the researcher may affect the results of study. Therefore, in the following studies we would try to invite the participants who have closer relationship with us, such as friends or relatives, because a closer relationship will make the participants be willing to explore more affective details, which will increase the efficiency of the studies and meet better the objectives of this study.

CONCEPT OF SOUNDCAPSULE

According to Wikipedia (<http://www.wikipedia.org/>), the definition of 'Time Capsule' is: "A time capsule is a historic cache of goods or information, usually intended as a method of communication with future people." (Time Capsule, 2011) Today people also use this method to keep some meaningful items and

when these items are re-opened someday in the future, people will re-experience the past feelings. Through the analysis of the above studies about the sound media, we know that the sound media are very useful to help people evoke their memories. Drawing an analogy to the concept of 'cool media and hot media' proposed by Marshall McLuhan (1964), compared with the image, the sound belongs to cool media which provide only a small number of detail information for auditory perception so that the listeners will create by themselves some complementary data and increase their participation. Therefore, based on such a concept, we want to design a 'time capsule', named as SoundCapsule, which focuses on sound media rather than a physical time capsule. We want to combine it with our everyday objects and adopt a random way to evoke our memories to provide us with different experiences from the ones given by the visual media.

SoundCapsule is mobile application software (App) that was developed on the Android platform. It is able to record sounds, set an irregular period of time and ring unexpectedly in the future. The reason why we choose the physical object mobile phone as the carrier of sound media is as follows: (1) Mobile phone is a modern essential item and it is portable so that it can be a tool to accept information by using intuitively the sense of hearing, and it's helpful for mixing the past sounds with the future contexts. As what Norman (2002) said, "The most convenient thing is to use something naturally without changing our living habits." That is why we don't want to design a new object. (2) Because the recalling of memories is like an everyday computing activity (Abowd & Myanttt, 2000), that is, it occurs or is triggered anytime in our daily life. The mobile phone is a portable object so that it allows the users to receive the sounds and feel surprised whenever the memories are represented naturally and unexpectedly anytime anywhere. The above-mentioned randomness is also a key point. For example, while walking on the street and hearing suddenly the theme song of the movie Ghost playing in a shop, you might suddenly remember that it is the song your boy-friend sang for you and it is the song of your love, and then you might re-experience immediately your past feelings.

SCENARIO

We will explain the process of using SoundCapsule software and show it by a piece of scenario (Figure5). Three months ago, Lili and her family had a trip in the countryside. They used SoundCapsule to record some fragments of their happy time, saved them in the music box of the SoundCapsule, and set a period of time, about three months later, to replay these fragments of the happy trip. Three months (or more) later, when Lili was reading in the living room, her mobile phone rang suddenly. Lili thought it must be a call from her friend, but when she answered the phone, she heard the sounds of the trip she and her family had three months ago and this unexpected phone call made Lili feel very excited and surprised because she had totally forgotten these fragments of sounds. This unexpected randomness is the goal of the design of SoundCapsule. It gives the users not only a re-experience of past memories but also a surprise of re-discovery.

Figure5. Usage of SoundCapsule. Lili used SoundCapsule App in her mobile phone to record some fragments of the sound in holiday and sent it to the future. She set a period of time and hoped that 3 months later she would re-hear these sounds. 3 months later, one night, Lili's mobile phone rang suddenly, she thought it's a phone call from a friend, but actually it was a piece of sound she had recorded. When she listened to this sound, she recalled some happy images of the past time.

Therefore, we want to explore two points in respect of this device: (1) Is this device able to recall past memories and represent past feelings? (2) How do the users feel when they receive unexpectedly the recorded past sounds? What do they recommend in respect of this device? In the next paragraph, we will describe the methods of the study of SoundCapsule.

METHODS

We invited ten participants who knew well how to use a smart phone, aged from 16 to 55. We chose these participants because we hoped the design would be acceptable for these generations in the future. Moreover, we knew that the sound perception varied with different generations and these different generations would give us more different advices and suggestions to help us to accomplish the future design.

We asked these participants to record the audio clips that they wanted to save in their daily life during the period of November 2010. We provided a recording device for each of them and asked them to return to us after two weeks. Two weeks later, we collected a total of 191 sounds clips. We hoped those record sounds would help to develop the relation between sound and memory. We hoped that it might allow us to get the insight from the study using sounds as a medium for memory to tell stories, especially without photos or videos.

After three more months, we put the sounds into the software application of SoundCapsule and provided an HTC mobile phone and a booklet for each of them to write their opinions during the period of 2 weeks. And then two weeks later, they were asked to return their booklets and phones back, and we held structured interviews with them. We selected qualitative research to study the data through interview and booklets. We collect data to compare the result and draw conclusions. We also interviewed the participants and the sharers about the experience of using SoundCapsule. In the end, we show the results and discuss the final conclusion.

Figure6. Mobile phones and booklets

Here, we have to explain that the sound materials for this study are the sounds recorded in the pre-

study. Thus we chose to use the previously recorded sound as the materials of this SoundCapsule study because more than 2 months have passed since the participants re-heard their own sounds. So we thought that they had probably forgotten the sounds and these materials were very well for study here.

RESULT

Participants were asked to join an in-depth interview after the study to share their experiences and feelings triggered by SoundCapsule.

TIME AND THE EXPECTATIONS OF USERS

The time setting of SoundCapsule is an approximate way. For example, setting 15 minutes would trigger a phone call around 15 minutes later. In our observation, when participants target to send sound clips within a short time, they will expect to “wait” for calls from SoundCapsule in mind at the very moment and it will have less fun and surprise. Jack (user1) said, “As I set the future delivery in a shorter time, therefore I will expect that there would be calls from SoundCapsule as soon as the cell phone rings, it is as expected of course, I have no particular feeling when receiving calls...” However, if the target is set upon a longer timeframe (ex: 3 days later) for SoundCapsule delivery, the expectation of participants will be decreased and they will even forget the SoundCapsule been set, and thus they will be surprised and amused by receiving the past sound. Mew (user6) said, “I soon forget the time being set 5 days later till the 3rd day...therefore I am surprised when I receive the sound at the moment! ... I realize immediately that I did send SoundCapsule to future me.” We found that the time being set will relate to user’s expectation and surprise. The longer time we set for the future, the lower the intentional expectation is, the sense of surprise is more strongly. The shorter time we set for the future, the higher the intentional expectation is, the lower the sense of surprise is.

In the meantime, there are users expressing that the behavior of time setting will also affect the mood and will seemingly result in negative impact. Ema (user7) said, “I will be waiting for calls from SoundCapsule and pay attention to the cell phone all the time...and will be scared of missing the past

sound...I am a bit uneasy about this.” However, such state is not what we intend to trigger. Therefore, instead of time setting by users, we will consider to make the system call users randomly to lower the intentional expectation and to enhance a sense of surprise.

PRESENT SOUND AND PAST SOUND

The most interesting part for users is a mixture of present sound (ringing tone called by friends or relatives at the very moment), and past sound (ringing tone sent by SoundCapsule). It appears while users wait for calls from SoundCapsule. One does not know whether the call is the present or past sound, and this will bring participants more fun and surprise. Below is an example of calls from SoundCapsule regarded as present calls by mistake. Kevien (user3) said, “I answer the call when the cell phone rings. I have been talking to the other side. However, the other side responds with an irrelevant answer, which confuses me a lot...until I hear the conversation between my daughters and me. Suddenly I realize that it is the conversation recorded when I drove to travel with my family members in the past ... I am really surprised at that time.” Weston (user8) said, “I’ve been hearing dogs barking and wondering why there is sound of dogs ...hereafter I remember that it is past sound I recorded when I took the pet on a walk with my brother.” What’s more interesting is, some participants were annoyed about receiving calls from SoundCapsule, because the participants did not realize that it is past sound. Cowboy (user4) said, “The call rang when I was typing the computer, I heard my girlfriend chatting with a man. I thought that she went out with a man and made call to me by mistake, I was a bit annoyed at that time. When I confirmed again, I realized that the man is me.”

Likewise, some participants regarded the calls from friends as calls from SoundCapsule by mistake. Jack (user1) said, “I saw an unknown incoming call and thought it is the sound from the past. However, A man yelled my name loudly when I answered the call, and soon I realized that it is from my friend...I was a bit shocked about it, totally out of my expectation.”

Moreover, some participants received the same sound recorded in the past at the same space. Mew

(user6) said, “It was very amazing. I recorded this sound clip on the platform where I stood earlier on, I was ready going home at that time...I did not expect that I receive the sound recorded on the platform I stand on now...I really don’t know the reason why I recorded...it was really funny. Just like time traveler...a feeling of going back to the past.”

The calls with inter-woven “present” and “past” sounds will lead to an unexpected and high sense of surprise, which are recognized by participants, and fulfill the purpose we expect from SoundCapsule design in the very beginning.

SOUND AND MEMORY TRIGGER

Some users said that the sounds aged for so long and became blurred, and failed to trigger memory immediately and directly. These sounds require listening for a period of time to be conscious of the sound in the past, and users will be surprised especially when they found that it is sound in the past at the very moment. Kiki (user5) said, “When I was going to bed and suddenly received a call, I thought it was a fraud call and made me scared when I heard a sound of motorbike. I realized that it is sound in the past when I continue listening, which really surprised and amused me.” However, sound will also stimulate the brain to enhance the accuracy of memory. Kiki (user5) said, “You can fully feel the emotion and state of everyone in a sound clip, it is different from images. ... Photos only show the appearance but sounds cover internal and external emotion.” Moreover, there will be a joy of re-discovery when one re-hears the past sound. Jerry (user9) said, “God! I am not conscious of having said such words ... how would I describe the thing this way? ... I am really surprised, is it really out of my mouth? ...”

We learn that sounds are difficult to memorize details, by observing the feedback of participants. The process of memory triggering by sound is slow and real, allowing sentiments to follow the tempo of sounds, with fluctuated contents to allow participants to re-experience the feeling in the past. Therefore the sound is of significant emotional effect.

DISCUSSION AND FINDINGS

ACTIVE AND PASSIVE

If users recall their memories in an active manner, it becomes a purposeful behavior. The meaning is that users already bear some thoughts in mind and want to recall more emotion, and then will search about related information. On the contrary, if users take action in a passive manner to accidentally receive external information to recall memory, a sense of curiosity will evoke to recall more information and details at the same time, with a sense of surprising as there is no expectation or certain intention. Jack (user1) said, “I am a bit unconscious about these sounds, however, there are images popping up in my mind when I suddenly listen to the past sound...and they create more association unexpectedly and make me want to flip over the photos at that time...” Ema (user7) said, “...when hearing the sound clips suddenly, I can almost imagine the sunshine coming from the window while having meals in the restaurant...there was also a cat lying on the table outdoors...If I only look at the photos, I think I will only pay attention to the figure and ignore other details.”

Therefore, we know that our memories will generate smooth images accordingly and will stimulate us to associate with more memories upon the sound played when we use the SoundCapsule to passively recall the memory. A certain timeline will be centered instead of associating with more memories if we proceed to recall memories in an active manner. Therefore in our point of view, active recall is a method to review the memory, mainly to recover memory, to deepen impression, and to remember certain events, while being passive is a way to evoke memory by re-experiencing the past emotion which were forgotten.

THE CONTENT OF THE SOUND MATERIAL

The sound clips used in this study are those recorded in pre- studies, and therefore participants have listened once before placing into the database of SoundCapsule. With certain impressions of these sound clips, the sense of surprise is somewhat reduced when re-hearing the sound material in a SoundCapsule. It is obvious that sound have a time

effectiveness and requires a longer interval of time to ensure being fully forgotten by the users while listening for the second time. Otherwise, the newly recorded sound material or the sounds recorded by the 3rd party will create a sense of surprise to interviewees through the SoundCapsule.

Moreover, the contents of sound materials are also important to memory recall. If meaningless sound means nothing to a participant, it fails to evoke emotion when rehearing it at random. Weston (user8) said, "I did not have ideas while recording the sound...just random recording...I hear the sounds of some dogs barking, a group of people talking ... I was probably taking a walk in the park at that time ... I cannot imagine how I felt at that time." This also poses an important question to us, how to motivate participants to record sounds. Therefore, how to guide and remind users to intentionally record sounds is of special importance.

USER SUGGESTIONS AND FEEDBACK

According to this study, a lot of users have consecutively expressed their suggestions and thoughts about the SoundCapsule, provided as a reference for our further revisions in the future.

MEMORY PLEASURE ENHANCEMENT

Concerning how to increase the pleasure of memory, some participants suggested that a sound be triggered according to space and events. For example, based on the event of birthday, when someone is having a birthday, the voice clip recorded on last birthday will play. On the other hand, when we revisit the same place, where we recorded a certain sound clip in the past, the sound will be triggered to play based on the location/space. However, the above goals might all need GPS and other technologies.

MOBILE PLATFORM

As the current study platform is Android, each participant needed a smart phone of Android system, and one had to insert SIM card into the cell phone we provided. Therefore, some interviewees were not used to the operation: "my cell phone is iPhone, it (Android) is inconvenient and unfamiliar to me ... I feel better to operate the cell phone platform of my

own, it will be natural and direct to me when I use it," and "...what I use is Windows-based cell phone, it takes time for me to get used to it while switching to Android system, it is not the cell phone I am used to after all."

It seems that it is troublesome for interviewees to use a platform they are not used to and it takes time for them to get used to a system of a different platform. Therefore, in the future, we will design versions that support different cell phones to allow users to operate on their own cell phones.

TIME OF RECEIVING SOUNDCAPSULE

Two participants suggested that the time of receiving SoundCapsule be set in terms of time interval (ex: morning, noon, evening). Although inaccurate time will lead to a sense of surprise, but sometimes the time of receiving is not appropriate and will reduce people's intention in answering the calls. For example, "... I need to work in the morning, therefore I prefer not to be disturbed when I am busy and in the meeting...therefore I will reject the calls or turn off the cell phone sometimes...However, till the evening time, I will be in a better mood if it rings with past sound heard when I am alone, perhaps it is a good time for memory recall when I am free." Therefore, the participants will be able to truly immerse themselves in the past memory with pleasure if it is set when people are free, which is important point to consider.

THE UNRECEIVED SOUND AND THE REPEATED SOUND

During the process of study, some participants failed to receive or missed the calls of SoundCapsule. Therefore participants would suggest connecting to voice mail for the sounds that don't received, allowing users to get into the voice mail to hear the past sound. Moreover, sometimes the users will hear the received sound repeatedly as the system makes calls to users by randomly selecting same voice clips. Therefore, some participants suggested to delete the received sound from database so as to enable a precious feeling to people for being aware of disappearance of voice, with a pulsation never reappears once you miss it.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The motivation that we design the SoundCapsule is primarily based on the fact that the sound is proved to be an effective material to trigger memory in our pre-studies, and it is also different from the effects of memory triggered by most of the visual media. We further develop our design by combining past sound with portable and tangible objects to trigger our memory. Most of the participants report positive feedback and are surprised and amused by this. Four characteristics can be identified after the SoundCapsule is evaluated by users: (1) expanding the scope of memory evocation; (2) creating a sense of surprise, recalling lost memories, and enhancing pleasure during the process of reminiscence; (3) starting a topic to share with others to facilitate social interaction; (4) providing a new way and new experience of recalling memory. However, these characteristics can be regarded as means and references to make a time capsule.

Moreover, in the future, we will not only make some revisions upon participants' suggestions, for example, leaving the time setup function to the remote server, rather than allowing users to proceed time setup to reduce the intentional expectation of users and increase a sense of surprise. Also, we will design cell phone apps that apply to different platforms to facilitate participants to execute SoundCapsule by their own cell phones.

Finally, we have conveyed our design concepts and methods in this paper, which have been successfully studied in the real living contexts of participants. This allows the sound media to recall our memory in a novel manner, which is what surprises and amuses many participants.

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